

Electronic Supplementary Information

High Proton Conductivity of a Bismuth Phosphonate Metal-Organic Framework with Unusual Topology

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Synthesis of the $\text{Py}(\text{PO}_3\text{H}_2)_4$ linker

The lab-made $\text{Py}(\text{PO}_3\text{H}_2)_4$ linker was synthesized following the Scheme S1:

Scheme S1. Synthetic route towards the preparation of $\text{Py}(\text{PO}_3\text{H}_2)_4$.

$\text{Py}(\text{Br})_4$:

$\text{Py}(\text{Br})_4$ was synthesized according to a published work with slight modifications.¹ In a 250 mL round-bottom flask, 2 g (9.88 mmol) of pyrene were dissolved in 60 mL of nitrobenzene at room temperature under constant magnetic stirring. 6.48 g of Br_2 (40.56 mmol) were added, and the resulting mixture was heated with a condenser at $120\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 h. After cooling to ambient temperature, acetone is added (approximately 50 mL) and the resulting yellowish $\text{Py}(\text{Br})_4$ solid was filtered, washed with acetone and dried at ambient conditions. Yield = 97%.

$\text{Py}(\text{PO}_3\text{Et}_2)_4$:

In a 30 mL microwave reactor, 0.6 g of $\text{Py}(\text{Br})_4$ (1.16 mmol), 0.1063 g of $[\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4]$ (8% based on the mol of $\text{Py}(\text{Br})_4$, 0.092 mmol) and 6 mL of triethyl phosphite were added and stirred for 1 min. Then, the mixture was put inside the microwave and heated following the next temperature program: i) heating up to $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ during 5 min; ii) keeping at $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 25 min; and iii) cooling down to $60\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

After the reaction, the reactor was placed overnight at ambient conditions, leading to the crystallization of the desired compound. The reactor was filled with petroleum ether, sonicated for 1 min and the resulting yellow solid was filtered. The obtained powder, denoted $\text{Py}(\text{PO}_3\text{Et}_2)_4$, was washed again by suspending it in 30 mL of petroleum ether and sonicated for few minutes in order to remove some residual triethyl phosphite and impurities. Finally, was filtered and dried at ambient conditions. Yield = 92%.

$\text{Py}(\text{PO}_3\text{H}_2)_4$:

1.43 g (1.92 mmol) of $\text{Py}(\text{PO}_3\text{Et}_2)_4$ and 80 mL of HCl 12 M were mixed and heated at reflux temperature in a 250 mL round-bottom flask for 24 h. The resulting solid was filtered and washed with a small amount of acetone. The obtained yellowish compound, termed as $\text{Py}(\text{PO}_3\text{H}_2)_4$, was then dried at 60 °C. Yield = 98%.

Scheme 2: Sulfonation reaction of PSU.

CCDC 2161748 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif, or by emailing data_request@ccdc.cam.ac.uk, or by contacting The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, U.K.; fax: + 44 1223 336033.

Stability tests carried out at room temperature were by suspending 20 mg of IEF-7 in 20 mL of the selected solutions (organic solvents, aqueous solutions at different pH). The initial pH of the aqueous samples was fixed with HCl (pH = 1.3) or NaOH (pH = 7.5, 10.5 and 12). The suspended solids were kept in sealed vials under stirring for 16 h. Then, the samples were collected by filtration. The liquid phase after the filtration was measured by UV-Vis spectroscopy in order to quantify the released linker.

Mechanical stability under pressure and the pelletization of the samples were carried out by applying 49 MPa of uniaxial pressure to 50 mg of the powdered sample by using a 6 mm diameter die.

Fig. S1: PXRD patterns of the materials obtained at different [Bi].

Fig. S2: PXRD patterns of the materials obtained at different L/M ratios.

Fig. S3: PXRD patterns of the materials obtained by using different Bi sources.

Fig. S4: PXRD patterns of the materials obtained at different temperatures.

Fig. S5: SEM image of IEF-7.

Fig. S6: TEM image of an IEF-7 crystal.

Table S1: Crystallographic parameters for the 3DED data of IEF-7. The data were collected from six individual crystals and merged together to give a higher completeness.

Empirical formula	$C_8BiO_6P_5$
Wavelength	0.0251 Å
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	$P\bar{1}$ (No. 2)
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 4.72$ Å $b = 9.62$ Å $c = 12.75$ Å, $\alpha = 107.84^\circ$ $\beta = 92.42^\circ$ $\gamma = 97.13^\circ$
Volume	544 Å ³
Z	2

Correlation coefficient of merged data (CC_1)	0.94
Index ranges	$-5 \leq h \leq 5$ $-11 \leq k \leq 11$ $-15 \leq l \leq 15$
Reflections collected	10251
Independent reflections	1634 [$R(\text{int}) = 0.2082$]
Completeness (to 0.8 Å resolution)	90 %
R_1 (ED model) [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.2104

Fig. S7: SBU of IEF-7. Bi, P, C, and O are represented in purple, orange, brown and red, respectively. Hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

Fig. S8: Bond distances in the Bi_2O_{10} SBU. Bi and O are represented in purple and red, respectively.

Fig. S9: Plausible structure obtained from classical geometry optimization for IEF-7 (up) (pink: P; purple: Bi, red: O, grey: C; white: H)

Fig. S10: Distances obtained for the H^+ in the structure obtained from Monte Carlo simulations (pink: P; purple: Bi, red: O, grey: C; white: H).

Fig. S11: N_2 sorption isotherm at 77K of IEF-7.

Fig. S12: Le Bail profile fitting of the IEF-7 structure.

Table S2: Structural parameters of IEF-7 obtained by EDT and by Le Bail refinement.

	EDT	PXRD
Space Group	<i>P</i> -1	<i>P</i> -1
a (Å)	4.72	4.82
b (Å)	9.62	9.45
c (Å)	12.75	12.63
α (°)	107.84	108.50
β (°)	92.42	92.26
γ (°)	97.13	97.15

Fig. S13: FTIR spectra of IEF-7 (blue) and Py(PO₃H₂)₄ linker (orange).

Fig. S14: TGA curve of IEF-7. The final residue was identified as Bi₂P₄O₁₃ by PXRD.

Fig. S15: VTPXRD of IEF-7.

Fig. S16: PXRD patterns of IEF-7 (1 mg/mL) after the stability tests in organic media.

Fig. S17: PXRD patterns and degradation quantification of IEF-7 (1 mg/mL) after the stability tests in aqueous media at different pH.

Fig. S18: PXRD patterns of IEF-7 before (blue) and after (red) applying 49 MPa.

Fig. S19: Impedance spectra of IEF-7 and IEF-7-SPSU 57 % at 40 °C and different RH.

Fig. S20: Conductivities values of IEF-7 at different RH% at 60 °C.

Table S3: Ultra-high proton conductivity values of different MOFs

MOF	Composition	Conductivity ($S \cdot cm^{-1}$) and conditions	Ref.
IEF-7	$Bi_2(Py(PO_3)_2(PO_3H)_2)$	$1.39 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (90 °C, 90% RH)	This work
IEF-7-SPSU 57%	$Bi_2(Py(PO_3)_2(PO_3H)_2)$ -SPSU 57%	$3.69 \cdot 10^{-3}$ (90 °C, 90% RH)	This work
1K_Eu	$K_3Y_{0.95}Eu_{0.05}(pptd)$	$1.89 \cdot 10^{-1}$ (94 °C, 98% RH)	2
Co-tri	$[Co(bpy)(H_2O)_4](Hbtc) \cdot (H_2O)_{1.5}$	$1.49 \cdot 10^{-1}$ (80 °C, 98% RH)	3
BUT-8-(Cr) A	$Cr_3(\mu_3-O)(H_2O)_3(NDC(SO_3H_{5/6})_2)_3$	$1.27 \cdot 10^{-1}$ (80 °C, 100% RH)	4
MIL-101-SO ₃ H	$Cr_3(O)(OH)(bdc-SO_3H)_3(H_2O)_2$	$1.16 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (80 °C, 100% RH)	4
UiO-66(SO ₃ H) ₂	$Zr_6O_4(OH)_4(bdc-(SO_3H)_2)_6$	$8.4 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (80 °C, 90% RH)	5
TfOH@MIL-101	TfOH@ $Cr_3(O)(OH)(bdc)_3(H_2O)_2$	$8.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (60 °C, 15% RH)	6
$[Gd(H_4nmp)(H_2O)_2] Cl.2H_2O$	$[Gd(H_4nmp)(H_2O)_2]Cl.2H_2O$	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (94 °C, 98% RH)	7
PCMOF2 _{1/2}	$[Na_3L_1]_{0.66}[Na_3H_3L_2]_{0.34} \cdot 0.75H_2O$	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (85 °C, 90% RH)	8
H ₂ SO ₄ @MIL-101	$H_2SO_4@Cr_3(O)(OH)(bdc)_3(H_2O)_2$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (150 °C, 0.13% RH)	9

$Py(PO_3H_2)_4$ = pyrene tetraphosphonic acid; H_6pptd = 5'-(4-phenylphosphonic acid)-[1,1':3',1''-terphenyl]-4,4''-diyl)diphosphonic acid; bpy = 4,4'-bipyridine; H_3btc = 1,2,4-Benzenetricarboxylic acid; $H_2NDC(SO_3H)_2$ = 4,8-disulfonyl-2,6-naphthalenedicarboxylic acid; $H_2BDC-SO_3Na$ = 2-Sulfoterephthalic acid monosodium salt; H_2BDC = terephthalic acid; $H_2BDC-SO_3Na$ = Nitritoltris(methylenephosphonic acid); H_6L_2 = 1,3,5- Benzenetriphosphonic acid.

Fig S21: VTF fitting of the conductivity data from the IEF and IEF-7 SPSU 57% at RH = 90%.

Fig. S22: Thermogravimetric analysis of IEF-7 at HR of 90%, overnight.

Fig. S23: Water sorption isotherm of IEF-7 at 25°C.

Fig. S24: Thermogravimetric vapor sorption analysis (TG-VSA) of IEF-7 (water, 90% HR).

Fig. S25: Description of the bonds network between water and H⁺ in the IEF-7 pore. The blue lines correspond to distances lower than 2.6Å illustrating the grotthus mechanism and the proton conductive pathways

Table S4: Parameters of the VTF Eq. (Eq. 2) obtained by fitting the conductivity data

VTF parameters	IEF-7	SPSU 57%	IEF-7-SPSU 57%
T_0 (K)	259	276	284
σ_0 (S·cm ⁻¹)	0.10	0.004	0.02
E_a^{VTF} (eV)	0.022	0.007	0.001

Fig. S28. PXRD patterns of IEF-7 (blue), IEF-7-SPSU 57% (red) and IEF-7-SPSU 100% (green).

Fig. S29. Nyquist plots of IEF-7 at 70% and 90% RH at different temperatures.

Fig. S30. Nyquist plots of the IEF-7-SPSU 57% at 70% and 90% RH at different temperatures.

Fig. S31: PXRD patterns of pelletized IEF-7 before (red) and after (green) the proton conducting measurements (including cyclability).

Fig. S32: FT-IR spectra of IEF-7 before (light blue) and after (green) the proton conducting measurements.

Fig. S33: PXRD patterns of the pelletized IEF-7-SPSU 57% before (navy) and after (orange) the conductivity measurements (including cyclability).

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